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Assembly Twin

D2.1: Simulation Campaign Plan

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Abstract:	<i>This deliverable outlines the simulation campaign plan for WP2, focusing on key physics-based models for manufacturing and operation processes of vanadium redox-flow and Li/Na-ion batteries. It identifies critical process steps, and the more relevant physical quantities. Process maps and technical model descriptions are provided to define interconnections and ensure eventual compatibility between connected models. These elements will guide the development of complete workflows, linking simulations of individual process steps into an integrated framework to represent manufacturing and operation phases for the two battery use cases.</i>
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Author list

Beneficiary	Name	Contact e-mail
POLITO	Gianluca Boccardo	gianluca.boccardo@polito.it
NMBU	Martin Thomas Horsch	martin.thomas.horsch@nmbu.no
IFPEN	Martin Petit	martin.petit@ifpen.fr
LOYOLA	Francisco Montero-Chacón	fmontero@uloyola.es
UKRI	Michael Seaton	michael.seaton@stfc.ac.uk
SIMULA	Eirik Valseth	eirikva@simula.no
ITWM	Jochen Zausch	jochen.zausch@itwm.fraunhofer.de
DTU	Ivano Eligio Castelli	ivca@dtu.dk
VANEVO	Andreas Linhart	andreas.linhart@vanevo.de

Reviewers List

Beneficiary	Name	Contact e-mail
NMBU	Martin Thomas Horsch	martin.thomas.horsch@nmbu.no

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Abbreviations and acronyms

CGA	Consortial general assembly
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
EAB	external advisory board
KER	key exploitable resource
NDA	non-disclosure agreement
PMB	project management board
PMO	project management officer
TMWG	technical management working group

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1. Executive summary

Description of the deliverable content and objectives

This document constitutes the first step in the activity of the multiphysics modelling and simulation workpackage (WP2) and delivers a plan of the simulations that are to be performed throughout the duration of the project. These models are the ones that have been identified to be the most important in the representation of the whole process regarding both the manufacturing step and the operation (i.e. charge/discharge) phase of the two use cases considered: Vanadium redox-flow batteries (VRFB) and Lithium (and Sodium)-ion batteries.

The necessary groundwork for the preparation of this simulation campaign plan is found in the finalized deliverables D6.1 regarding the use-case requirements, and D4.1 regarding the data and infrastructure requirements. The first crucial step was to expand and detail the work which was present in a seminal form in D6.1 on the identification of the most important phases of these processes and the more important quantities to be considered: both in terms of them being important metrics for the evaluation of the techno-economical performance of a process, or them being information and data which have been found to have the greater impact on the mentioned metrics, and as such would constitute prime candidates for parameter optimization processes. The updated schematic overview for both these processes are found in the following two pages.

The provided schemas have been used by each unit participating in WP2 to identify the relevant physics-based models to be employed (and possibly develop) and will serve as a guide for the next step of the modelling activity in the BatCAT project, the construction of full simulation workflows. This objective (itself connected to the necessity of building parallel digital twins of the processes in WP5) will be attained by structuring a graph of the relevant process steps (and the connected physics-based model) composed by the presently presented planned models, together with the necessary mapping tools needed to relay information from one model to another in the appropriate form. As such, this work will serve as the basis for the preparation of the two workflows (for each use case) to be delivered by M27 in the finalized integrated multiphysics modelling workflows in D2.3.

In the core of the present D2.1 deliverable, contained in Section 2 of this document, each identified model can be found, described first in their purposes and underlying methodology, and secondly from a more purely technical point of view for software deployment purposes.

This list of scientific models, together with their implementation details, constitutes the current simulation campaign plan for BatCAT.

Schematic overview of the Li/Na-ion use case quantities relevant for modelling

2. List of modelling tools

This section gathers the list of the modelling tools identified by the partners in WP2 to be the most appropriate to build physics-based digital twins of the manufacturing and operation processes related to both the VRFB and Li/Na-ion use cases.

Each model entry is structured to have two main sections. The first section explains, in a free form, the context of the research activity of the unit proposing the model, its scientific objectives, and the general methodology for the implementation of the computational model. If necessary, the relevant physical equations and material relations are offered, together with appropriate literature references.

The second section has a more fixed structure in order to facilitate both comparison and technical analysis of the models, and also to help the implementation of the same in a way that would allow for these codes horizontal interoperability, i.e. allowing for as simple and as automated as possible operation of transferring model results between one model to the other. Even more importantly, this will also inform the activity of development of accurate digital twins as prescribed by the action plan regarding WP5.

In this tabular section, the *Model Technical Sheet* carries information on the model seen as a computer code for means of installation/use: licensing issues vs. FOSS codes, architecture requirements statements, and runtime CPU access and memory usage are listed. The following *Model Information Flow* carries the information which are needed for the model to run and (*inputs*) and just as importantly the simulation results (*outputs*). These are described both as a file structure summary, again to aid in the organization of structured workflows, and as a parallel description of the information carried in those files from both a tensorial (i.e. dimensionality) perspective and scientific one in terms of units of measurement.

It has to be noted that in the present document only computational codes implementing relevant physics-based models are listed: at this stage, pre- and post-processors are not explicitly gathered (only some are listed), as this will be done in a second stage - for which the planning of the simulation campaign and the current survey of modelling tools was needed. The full list of codes and the actual technical implementation of their connections will use this information and be built into complete workflows, to be finalized in the upcoming deliverable D2.3, containing all simulations models and workflows.

- **Methodology**

The scripts and software described in this document are utilized to generate a 3D model of a battery half-cell in COMSOL Multiphysics. COMSOL employs the finite element method, a numerical approach that is highly effective for solving complex geometries and multi-physics problems. This software offers a comprehensive suite of tools, including a user-friendly graphical interface that allows users to define models, apply boundary conditions, and analyze results with ease. It also supports battery-specific simulations and features an application programming interface (API) in Java, which is particularly useful for automating processes such as the generation of electrodes. The micro-scale 3D modeling of Lithium-ion batteries is centered on the local numerical resolution of the charge and mass conservation of intercalated lithium and lithium ion respectively within the electrodes and the electrolyte. It has to be noted that in this model we are not focusing on the degradation phenomena that happen in a lithium-ion battery, the systems are considered ideal and therefore we are not considering side reactions like the Solid Electrolyte Inter-phase (SEI) formation.

The charge conservation is implemented through a steady state Ohm's law:

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{K}^S \nabla \phi^S) = 0$$

while the mass conservation is expressed through Fick's law, which describes the diffusion behavior of the lithium ions within the solid phases:

$$\frac{\partial c^S}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{D}^S \nabla c^S)$$

In parallel, the transport equations related to the charge and mass conservation of Lithium ions in the electrolyte are solved using concentrated solution theory as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial c^\ell}{\partial t} &= \nabla \cdot \left[\left(\mathbf{D}^\ell - \frac{2RT}{F^2} \left(1 + \frac{d(\ln f_\pm)}{d(\ln c^\ell)} \right) (1-t_+) t_+ \mathbf{K}^\ell \frac{1}{c^\ell} \right) \nabla c^\ell + \frac{t_+}{F} \mathbf{K}^\ell \nabla \phi^\ell \right], \\ 0 &= \nabla \cdot \left[\left(-\frac{2RT}{F} (1-t_+) \mathbf{K}^\ell \frac{1}{c^\ell} \right) \nabla c^\ell + \mathbf{K}^\ell \nabla \phi^\ell \right], \end{aligned}$$

where c^ℓ is the lithium-ion concentration in the electrolyte and ϕ^ℓ is the electrolyte potential, D_ℓ and K_ℓ are the diffusion and the electric conductivity coefficients respectively. R is the gas constant, T is the temperature, F is the Faraday constant. Finally, t_+ is the lithium-ion transference number, and f_\pm is the mean molar activity.

The main script driving the simulation is named **Script.class**, which acts as the central point of control, organizing the program into classes and their corresponding methods. Three key classes — **GeometryConstruction.class**, **PhysicsDefinition.class**, and **PostProcessing.class** — are called by this script to handle specific tasks. The workflow is structured into several stages to ensure that each aspect of the modeling process is handled systematically and efficiently.

The first stage of the workflow is the variable initialization. During this step, input files are read and processed to extract essential information required for the simulation. This phase ensures that the inputs are formatted correctly and consistent with the simulation requirements. For instance, the script includes a mechanism to prevent the generation of particles outside the defined domain of interest, ensuring accurate geometrical representation. One input file at this stage is **EquilibriumPotential.txt**, which is formatted as a two-column float array. The first column represents the state of charge, while the second contains the corresponding equilibrium potential values. The file is read into a $2 \times N$ float array, where N is the number of rows. Other input files include **Setup.txt** and **PhysicalProperties.txt**. The **Setup.txt** file provides key simulation parameters such as the type of electrode, mesh refinement levels, tolerance values, and the outputs requested by the user. If any parameter is missing from this file, the script assigns default values to maintain the simulation's continuity. The **PhysicalProperties.txt** file contains the physico-chemical properties necessary for the half-cell battery model. These are stored in a "String-float-String" format, where each entry includes the variable name, its numerical value, and a brief description, respectively.

Figure 1. a) Cathode half-cell geometry. b) Concentration contour plot.

Once initialization is complete, the process transitions to geometry construction. In this stage, methods from the **GeometryConstruction** class are used to define the spatial arrangement of particles based on data from **Geometry.txt**. This file contains M rows, one for each particle, and four columns: the X , Y , and Z coordinates of each particle's center (in meters) and the particle radius. After generating the particle arrangement, the script extracts a central portion of the particle package to define the electrode and positions a separator on top of it. The meshing process follows next, guided by the criteria specified in **Setup.txt**, ensuring accurate spatial discretization. The **PhysicsDefinition** class is then invoked to define the governing equations and boundary conditions for each domain. This involves applying the appropriate physical laws and ensuring that the equations accurately represent the behavior of the system. Finally, the simulation is executed, and methods from the **PostProcessing** class are used to generate the desired outputs. These results are saved in the working directory as a **Model.mph** file, which can be opened in the COMSOL GUI for further analysis or manual verification.

With the geometry prepared, the script uses methods from the **PhysicsDefinition** class to define the equations and boundary conditions for each domain of the model. Once this step is complete, the simulation is run. After the computational process, methods from the **PostProcessing** class are invoked to generate the specified outputs. The results are saved in the working directory as a **Model.mph** file, which is compatible with the COMSOL GUI and can be used for further post-processing or manual verification of the simulation setup.

- **Model technical sheet**

Name of the code	COMSOL Multiphysics
Version of the code to be integrated	6.3
Partner(s) involved	POLITO
Contact person(s)	Gianluca BOCCARDO (gianluca.boccardo@polito.it)
Nature of the software program: solver, pre-processor, post-processor, homogenization tool...	Pre-processor, solver, post-processor
OS: Windows/Linux and eventually Linux distribution: any, Debian, Suze, Fedora, Ubuntu, Linux Mint, Gentoo ...	<i>Linux: Ubuntu 22.04+; Windows: 10+</i>
Minimum memory requirement	4 GB
Major software requirement	none, libraries already present.
Access mode to the code: library, executable	Executable
Licence (free or commercial, GPL, LGPL)	Commercial
Open-source or not	No
The specific language(s) in which the code is written :C, C++, Fortran, Python	Java
What kind of API is proposed (one function, several functions) ; for each used function, give a short description	None
Execution with single- or multiple-calls	Single call.
Execution mode : sequential, parallel, distributed	Sequential and parallel (OpenMPI)
Whether compilation is necessary for each run	No
addendum	-
Website	https://www.comsol.it/

- **Model information flow : inputs and outputs**

- **File structure**

File name	Geometry
Extension	txt
Short description	Spatial characterization of the electrode particles.
File structuration formats*	Four columns of float numbers separated by single space.
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Input

Name of file	Setup
Extension	txt
Short description	Contains information about the type of simulation (e.g. “electrode type = cathode”) or regarding physical properties (e.g. “solid diffusivity = constant”).
File structuration formats*	Plain text
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Input

File name	EquilibriumPotential
Extension	txt
Short description	Equilibrium potential function of the state of charge.
File structuration formats*	Two columns of float numbers separated by single space.
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Input

File name	PhysicalProperties
Extension	txt
Short description	Values of the physical properties of the model, such as electrical conductivity, diffusivity etc
File structuration formats*	Three columns (variable name, value, description) separated by single space.
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Input

File name	Script
Extension	class
Short description	Script for the electrode generation in COMSOL
File structuration formats*	Plain text
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Code

File name	GeometryConstruction
Extension	class
Short description	Script that contains the methods for the geometry generation in COMSOL
File structuration formats*	Plain text
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	code

File name	PhysicsDefinition
Extension	class
Short description	Script that contains the methods for the physic-chemical definitions in COMSOL
File structuration formats*	Plain text
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Code

File name	PostProcessing
Extension	class
Short description	Script that contains the methods for the post processing operations in COMSOL
File structuration formats*	Plain text
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Code

○ **Physical quantities : type and description**

Inputs	Type	File
Solid electrical conductivity [S/m]	Scalar	Physicalproperties.txt
Liquid electrolyte conductivity [S/m]	Scalar	Physicalproperties.txt
Solid diffusivity [m ² /s]	Scalar	Physicalproperties.txt
Liquid diffusivity [m ² /s]	Scalar	Physicalproperties.txt
Equilibrium curve [V]	Array 2×N (N: dataset length)	EquilibriumPotential.txt
Geometry details [m]	Array 4×N (N: dataset length)	Geometry.txt

Outputs	Type	File
Charge/Discharge curve	Array 2×N (N: dataset length)	DischargeCurve.txt
Intercalated lithium contour plot	Image	ContourPlot.png
Simulation file	File	Model.mph

DFT simulations of SEI formation in Li/Na-ion batteries

- **Objective**

To describe the formation of the solid electrolyte interface (SEI) of Li/Na-ion batteries. The overall protocol is described in our previous work on the SEI formation on Li-ion system [1]. The approach will be extended to Na-ion batteries.

- **Methodology**

- 1) Molecular simulations at the atomistic scale using Density Functional Theory (DFT) of the pure-metallic electrode surface (Li/Na) and the liquid electrolyte (mainly ethylene-carbonate -EC-) will be performed. The main idea is to simulate the decomposition reactions of EC liquid electrolyte to form the organic layer of the SEI over the Li/Na surface, and over the first inorganic slab component. The initial nanometric system is described at the left in Figure 1.
- 2) DFT simulations will be performed by means of the Vienna ab initio simulation package VASP 6.3 [2] using the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof functional (PBE) [3] with dispersion interactions correction using the density-dependent dispersion dDsC [4], and the projector-augmented plane-wave (PAW) pseudopotential to describe core and valence electrons. Convergence criteria for the calculations are selected to 10^{-6} eV and 0.03 eV/Å, for electronic self-consistency iterations and ionic relaxation loop, respectively. A Fermi smearing with a width of 0.03 eV will be used. Spin polarized calculations will be performed for radical species. The cut-off energy for the plane-wave-basis will be set to 600 eV.
- 3) To obtain the energy barriers (E_b), as described for Li-ion battery at the right of Figure 1, the optimized geometries of reactants and products will be used as inputs to infer the minimum energy path (MEP) connecting them. The nudged elastic band method (NEB) [5] will be used to find a more accurate MEP and a possible transition state (TS) structure by creating 8 images between the initial and final states.

The Nudged Elastic Band (NEB) method is a computational technique used to find the minimum energy path (MEP) and transition states between two stable states in a system, typically in the context of atomic simulations. This method is particularly useful in the study of chemical reactions and phase transitions where understanding the pathway and the energy barriers is crucial.

In the NEB method, a series of "images" of the system are created between the initial and final states. These images are not actual pictures but rather representations of the system at different states along the reaction pathway. The images are then connected by imaginary springs to form an elastic band. The key idea is to allow these images to move under the influence of the force derived from the potential energy surface of the system, while the springs maintain them evenly spaced along the path.

The "nudging" part of the method involves adjusting the forces acting on the images. The true force that derives from the potential energy surface is modified by removing components that would pull the images off the path and by adding spring forces that keep the images

distributed along the path. This results in each image moving to a position where the force is minimized, leading to the discovery of the MEP. The force on each image is given by:

$$F_i = -\nabla V(R_i) + k(R_{i+1} - R_{i-1} - 2R_i)$$

where F_i is the total force on image i , V is the potential energy (i.e.: the electronic energy from DFT calculations), R_i is the position of image i , and k is the spring constant.

The NEB method is widely used because it can efficiently find the MEP without requiring a priori knowledge of the transition states, making it a powerful tool in materials science, chemistry, and physics for studying complex transformations.

- Once the potential candidate for a TS is identified, to ensure the nature of the potential candidate as a TS, a vibrational frequency calculation will be performed. In the case of TS, only one imaginary frequency should be obtained, corresponding to the (chemical) reaction coordinate of interest.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the physical system studied in this work, containing the Li^0 -anode, the crystalline inorganic and the amorphous organic layers and the bulk electrolyte phase (left). Reaction energy profile (and energy barriers E_b in red) for ethylene carbonate (EC) decomposition reactions in isolation (black) and over Li_2CO_3 (001) (blue) (right). Images taken from ref [1].

Required physical/chemical Input data: molecular geometry of EC electrolytes, molecular structure of Na_2CO_3 (001) surface.

Expected Output data: E_b of key molecular degradation reactions on isolation and over Na_2CO_3 surface for Na-ion system.

- **Model technical sheet**

Name of the code	VASP
Version of the code to be integrated	6.3
Partner(s) involved	IFPEN
Contact person(s)	Manuel Corral Valero Manuel.corral-valero@ifpen.fr ,
Nature of the software program: solver, pre-processor, post-processor, homogenization tool...	Solver (provides solutions for the Kohn-Sham equations of DFT), though can take part in a homogenization workflow when calculating materials properties from microscopic simulations.
OS: Windows/Linux and eventually Linux distribution: any, Debian, Suze, Fedora, Ubuntu, Linux Mint, Gentoo ...	Windows/Linux (Typically runs on Linux distributions such as Debian, SUSE, Fedora, Ubuntu, Linux Mint, Gentoo, and others).
Minimum memory requirement	8 GB of RAM (may vary depending on the size and complexity of the simulation).
Major software requirement	MPI (Message Passing Interface) for parallel computing, LAPACK, and BLAS libraries for linear algebra operations, and other dependencies like FFT libraries (FFTW) for fast Fourier transforms.
Access mode to the code: library, executable	Executable
Licence (free or commercial, GPL, LGPL)	Commercial
Open-source or not	No
The specific language(s) in which the code is written :C, C++, Fortran, Python	C, C++ and Fortran.
What kind of API is proposed (one function, several functions) ; for each used function, give a short description	VASP does not provide a traditional API but offers interfaces and integration with various tools such as Python scripts for automation and data analysis (e.g., pymatgen, ASE).
Execution with single- or multiple-calls	Single call for each run (though the input can be varied and multiple simulations can be run in a batch process).
Execution mode : sequential, parallel, distributed	Sequential and parallel (OpenMPI)

Whether compilation is necessary for each run	No
addendum	-
Website	https://www.vasp.at/

- **Model information flow : inputs and outputs**
 - **File structure**

File name	POSCAR
Extension	txt
Short description	VASP input file with the models' atomic coordinates
File structuration formats*	A header, a multiplication factor for the box cell vecors (default set to 1.0), the periodic box cell vectors, a line with the atom types, the X, Y, Z coordinates of each atom
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Input

Name of file	KPOINTS
Extension	txt
Short description	VASP input file. Number of points in each direction the reciprocal space to be considered in the DFT calculation
File structuration formats*	Plain text
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Input

File name	POTCAR
Extension	Txt
Short description	VASP input file. Plane-waves basis set and core-electron pseudopotentials for each atom type in the system.
File structuration formats*	Concatenation of several provided by the VASP team to describe atoms' electronic structure.

Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Input

File name	INCAR
Extension	Txt
Short description	VASP input file. Parameters for the DFT calculations and the DFT based geometry optimizations and NEB calculations.
File structuration formats*	Each line contains an entry with a tag and its specified value in the format tag = value Tags can adopt numerical, alphanumerical and Boolean values (see VASP webpage for further information).
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Input

File name	OUTCAR
Extension	Txt
Short description	VASP output file. Evolution of the iterative procedure of the calculation and the results: atomic coordinates, total energy of the system, interatomic energies and (for frequency calculations) values of the Hessian matrix. The file also contains a recap of the input settings.
File structuration formats*	Plain text. Each section has self-explanatory headings.
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	output

File name	vasprun
Extension	xml
Short description	Same as the OUTCAR file (see above) but in xml format (more convenient for scripting purposes).
File structuration formats*	Xml formatted plain text.

Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	output

References:

- 1) Bin Jassar, M.; Michel, C.; Abada, S.; De Bruin, T.; Tant, S.; Nieto-Draghi, C.; Steinmann, S. N. A Joint DFT-kMC Study To Model Ethylene Carbonate Decomposition Reactions: SEI Formation, Growth, and Capacity Loss during Calendar Aging of Li-Metal Batteries. *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2023**, *6* (13), 6934–6945
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- 3) Perdew, J. P.; Burke, K.; Ernzerhof, M. Generalized Gradient Approximation Made Simple [*Phys. Rev. Lett.* *77*, 3865 (1996)]. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 1997, *78*, No. 1396.
- 4) Steinmann, S. N.; Corminboeuf, C. Comprehensive Benchmarking of a Density-Dependent Dispersion Correction. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 2011, *7*, 3567–3577. Steinmann, S. N.; Corminboeuf, C. A Generalized-Gradient Approximation Exchange Hole Model for Dispersion Coefficients. *J. Chem. Phys.* 2011, *134*, 044117.
- 5) Henkelman, G.; Uberuaga, B. P.; Jónsson, H. A Climbing Image Nudged Elastic Band Method for Finding Saddle Points and Minimum Energy Paths. *J. Chem. Phys.* 2000, *113*, 9901–9904.

Continuum modelling of Li/Na-ion

- **Objective**

Model the formation, performance and aging behaviour of LIB and NIB using physics based modelling. This will be performed thanks to a simplified DFN [1] or SPM-e modelling approach. Consequently, the model will account for main mechanisms occurring in batteries and several aging mechanisms such as SEI formation, reversible Li or Na plating and positive electrode dissolutions will be taken into account.

- **Context**

IFPEN is developing 1D cell scale modelling using the Siemens Industry Software Simcenter Amesim software for which it codevelops a dedicated library for Electrical Storage [2]. In this library 2 simplifications of the negative/separator/positive arrangement are available as shown in Figure 2. In the DFN model (b) the cell microstructure is represented by spheres distributed between the separator and the separator in both electrodes. The more simplified SPM-e model considers only 1 mean particle in both electrodes. The 2 modelling approaches are solving the same equations and will differ mainly in computational time and validity domains. Overall P2D and SPM-e approaches represent a good balance between model computational times and accuracy.

Figure 2: DFN, SPM-e simplifications [3]

- **Methodology**

The main equations solved in these models are indicated in the Table 1. The main purpose of this model is to compute the voltage of the cell as follows:

$$U = \phi_s(L) - \phi_s(0)$$

Several variables are necessary to obtain this desired value. First of all, solid concentrations are computed thanks to equation (1), Li⁺ concentration in the electrolyte is obtained from equation (3). Between these 2, Li charge transfer is governed by Butler-Volmer equation (5) evaluating the current transfer reaction kinetic between solid phase and liquid phase. Besides solid and liquid concentrations, this kinetic requires, solid and liquid potentials obtained through solid charge and liquid phase conservations (resp. (2) and (4)) and the electrode potential. This value is evaluated thanks to an expression, or a look-up table given by the user.

Table 1 : Equations representing the electrochemical cell model

Electrochemical phenomena	Governing equations	Boundary conditions	Eq.
Solid-phase Li-ion mass conservation	$\frac{\partial c_s}{\partial t} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 D_s \frac{\partial c_s}{\partial r} \right) = 0$	$\begin{aligned} D_s \frac{\partial c_s}{\partial r} \Big _{r=0} &= 0 \\ -D_s \frac{\partial c_s}{\partial r} \Big _{r=R_s} &= \frac{j_f}{a_s F} \end{aligned}$	(1)
Solid-phase Li-ion charge conservation	$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\sigma^{eff} \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial z} \right) - j_f = 0$	$\begin{aligned} -\sigma^{eff} \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial z} \Big _{z=0} &= 0 \\ -\sigma^{eff} \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial z} \Big _{z=L} &= \frac{I}{A_{sep}} \end{aligned}$	(2)
Liquid-phase Li-ion mass conservation	$\frac{\partial \varepsilon_e c_e}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(D_e^{eff} \frac{\partial c_e}{\partial z} \right) - (1 - t_+) \frac{j_f}{F} = 0$	$\frac{\partial c_e}{\partial z} \Big _{z=0} = \frac{\partial c_e}{\partial z} \Big _{z=L} = 0$	(3)
Liquid-phase Li-ion charge conservation	$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\kappa^{eff} \frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\kappa_D^{eff} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \ln c_e \right) + j_f = 0$	$\frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial z} \Big _{z=0} = \frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial z} \Big _{z=L} = 0$	(4)
Charge-transfer reaction kinetics	$j_f = a_s i_o \left\{ \exp \left(\frac{(1 - \alpha) F \eta_k}{RT} \right) - \exp \left(- \frac{\alpha F \eta_k}{RT} \right) \right\}$	-	(5)
Exchange current density	$i_o = k_o c_e^{1-\alpha} (c_{s,max} - c_{s,surf})^{1-\alpha} c_{s,surf}^\alpha$	-	(6)
Solid-phase electrode potential	$\eta_k = \phi_s - \phi_e - U_{ref}$	-	(7)
Equilibrium electrode potential	$U_{ref} = E_{ref} \left(\frac{c_{s,surf}}{c_{s,max}} \right)$	-	(8)
Effective liquid phase Li ⁺ ion diffusivity	$D_e^{eff} = D_e \varepsilon_e^{Brugg}$	-	(9)

Liquid phase ionic conductivity	$\kappa^{eff} = \kappa_e \varepsilon_e^{Brugg}$	-	(10)
Liquid phase ionic diffusional conductivity	$\kappa_D^{eff} = \frac{2RT}{F} \kappa^{eff} (t_+ - 1) \left(1 + \frac{d \ln f_{\pm}}{d \ln c_e} \right)$	-	(11)
Solid-phase electronic conductivity	$\sigma^{eff} = \varepsilon_s \sigma_s$	-	(12)
Interfacial surface area	$a_s = \frac{3\varepsilon_s}{R_s}$	-	(13)

As this model is a lumped approach of the battery, the microstructure is not fully described. Only simple descriptors are used to account for main microstructure impact:

- Mean particle radius
- Electrode porosity
- Electrode tortuosity through a Bruggeman correlation

- **Aging modelling**

Several modelling submodels are available or in advanced implementation into Simcenter Amesim library. In version 2410 released in October 2024, SEI formation [4] and reversible Li-plating [5] were implemented accounting for loss of Li inventory in the negative electrode. In the next year release, a positive electrode dissolution model [6] has been implemented.

Several further models have been investigated in MODALIS² project including mechanically induced aging and will be investigated if needed in BATCAT project.

All these models plug onto the DFN model described above by using computed variables such as solid concentrations, electrolyte concentrations and potentials and in turn change the behaviour of the nominal model by adding degradation reactions currents in the charge balance and/or modifying quantities such as active material volume fractions (loss of active material) or porosity (interface growth)

Parameters set

As seen in Table 1, several parameters are needed to run this model. Many of them are at least temperature-dependant parameters. Such parameters are implemented into the model thanks to Simcenter Amesim user interface. Preestablished dependencies (temperature, concentration...) are already in place but can be modified by creating a fit for purpose BATCAT dedicated model.

Expected output data

Output variables are of 2 types. Internal variables are computed inside the model and can be accessed either thanks to Simcenter Amesim GUI or retrieved through dedicated scripts in Python or Matlab. Externa variables are linked to model ports and can be used within Simcenter

Amesim sketch to feed other models with information (eg. Generated heat flow rate used in thermal model). External variables are also accessible via the GUI or dedicated scripts.

The main outputs of Simcenter Amesim battery models are the cell voltage and its generated heat flow rates which are used for charge/discharge control and thermal modelling.

- **Model technical sheet**

Name of the code	Simcenter Amesim
Version of the code to be integrated	2410 and +
Partner(s) involved	IFPEN
Contact person(s)	Martin PETIT (martin.petit@ifpen.fr)
Nature of the software program: solver, pre-processor, post-processor, homogenization tool...	Pre-processor, solver, post-processor
OS: Windows/Linux and eventually Linux distribution: any, Debian, Suze, Fedora, Ubuntu, Linux Mint, Gentoo ...	<i>Linux</i> : Ubuntu 22.04+; <i>Windows</i> : 10+
Minimum memory requirement	4 GB
Major software requirement	MinGW GCC 13.1.0 (supplied with Simcenter Amesim) Intel Compiler (19.0 update 6 or above) Microsoft Visual C++ (versions 2015 up to 2022)
Access mode to the code: library, executable	Executable
Licence (free or commercial, GPL, LGPL)	Commercial, FNL
Open-source or not	No
The specific language(s) in which the code is written :C, C++, Fortran, Python	C
What kind of API is proposed (one function, several functions) ; for each used function, give a short description	FMU Scripting (Python, Matlab VBA)
Execution with single- or multiple-calls	Single call.
Execution mode : sequential, parallel, distributed	Sequential and parallel

Whether compilation is necessary for each run	No
addendum	-
Website	https://plm.sw.siemens.com/en-US/simcenter/systems-simulation/amesim/

- **Model information flow : inputs and outputs**

File name	SimulationSketch
Extension	ame
Short description	Ame file generated from Simcenter Amesim containing all information on the simulation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amesim Sketch • Input parameters • Results • Coomplied code
File structuration formats*	Zip
Storage format*	NA
Input/Output/Code	Input/Output/Code

Model inputs

Input	Type	File
General parameters		
electrode area	scalar	embedded in *.ame
cell capacity	scalar	embedded in *.ame
Electrode parameters		
electrode thickness	scalar	embedded in *.ame
insertion rate at soc 0%	scalar	embedded in *.ame
electrode effective conductivity	expression f(T)	embedded in *.ame
electrode double layer capacitance	scalar	embedded in *.ame
electrolyte volume fraction	scalar	embedded in *.ame
active material volume fraction	scalar	embedded in *.ame

electrode particle radius	scalar	embedded in *.ame
electrolyte phase Bruggeman coefficient	scalar	embedded in *.ame
maximum solid concentration	scalar	embedded in *.ame
solid phase diffusivity	expression f(T,C)	embedded in *.ame
reaction rate constant	expression f(T)	embedded in *.ame
charge equilibrium potential	table or expression f(x)	dedicated *.data file
discharge equilibrium potential	table or expression f(x)	dedicated *.data file
entropic coefficient	table or expression f(x)	dedicated *.data file
charge transfer reaction coefficient	scalar	embedded in *.ame
Electrolyte parameters		
rest concentration	scalar	embedded in *.ame
electrolyte conductivity	expression f(T,C)	embedded in *.ame
electrolyte diffusivity	expression f(T,C)	embedded in *.ame
transference number	expression f(T,C)	embedded in *.ame
Seperator parameters		
thickness	scalar	embedded in *.ame
electrolyte volume fraction	scalar	embedded in *.ame
electrolyte phase Bruggeman coefficient	scalar	embedded in *.ame
SEI formation parameters		
initial capacity loss due to SEI formation	scalar	embedded in *.ame
solvent bulk concentration	scalar	embedded in *.ame
potential for solvent reduction	scalar	embedded in *.ame
SEI density	scalar	embedded in *.ame
SEI reaction charge transfer coefficient	scalar	embedded in *.ame
SEI molar mass	scalar	embedded in *.ame
SEI reaction rate constant	expression f(C,T)	embedded in *.ame
SEI solvent diffusivity	expression f(T)	embedded in *.ame
SEI layer conductivity	expression f(T)	embedded in *.ame
Li plating parameters		
charge transfer coefficient for plating/stripping	scalar	embedded in *.ame
lithium plating/stripping kinetic rate constant	expression f(T)	embedded in *.ame
dead lithium kinetic constant	scalar	embedded in *.ame

References

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<https://doi.org/10.1039/d2cp00417h>.
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Electrode-scale charge-discharge simulations of Lithium-Ion cells

Since the pore and particle morphology of the electrodes have a strong impact on the performance of a cell, we apply a model that explicitly takes into account the three-dimensional microstructure and is able to describe the transport of lithium ions within the different material phases of a cell. As a result, not only the macroscopic cell performance can be predicted but also localized effects that are specific to given microstructural features can be investigated (eg. Plating risk, influence of binder distribution, etc.).

In the following picture the simulation domain is sketched to illustrate the different material domains that are considered for electron and lithium transport:

Figure 3: Illustration of the simulation domain for electrode-resolved cell simulations with BEST.

- **Methodology**

As is obvious from the picture the full cell can be considered. However, in the lateral dimensions the model is restricted to a representative part in order to be computationally feasible. On this scale, the processes inside the cell are described by a continuum model for the concentration of lithium ions $c(\vec{x}, t)$ and potentials $\phi(\vec{x}, t)$ based on the underlying conservation equations for species and charge

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \vec{N} = 0$$

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{j} = 0.$$

The ion fluxes \vec{N} and current densities \vec{j} are given by a constitutive equation of the respective material domains and contain number of material-specific parameters, which might depend on the local state-of-charge or the salt concentration. The different domains are coupled by suitable interface conditions. Most importantly, the interface between active material and electrolyte has to be mentioned, since there the Lithium intercalation reaction occurs. This reaction is described by the Butler-Volmer-equation, which describe the non-linear relationship between interface concentrations and potentials with the intercalation current. A special case is the carbon-binder-domain (cbd): unlike the other materials the cbd consists of conductive additives, binder and pores on a much finer scale than can be reasonably resolved here. Therefore, cbd is treated an effective, porous medium. Further model additions include (among

others) the computation of heat generation during battery operation or the simulation of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy.

The coupled system of non-linear partial differential equations are discretized spatially using the finite volume method on a Cartesian grid which allows for the consideration of complex particle and pore shapes. The time-dependence take into account fully implicitly by a backward Euler scheme. The resulting linearized set of equations is implemented into ITWM's dedicated "Battery and Electrochemistry Simulation Tool" (BEST), which is an inhouse code implemented in C++.

For generation of the microstructure oftentimes the software GeoDict by Math2Market is applied which can segment 3d CT-scans or create complex microstructures using stochastic algorithms. Due to the very simple geometry input format of BEST also other formats (eg. From a production simulation) could be quickly adapted.

The transient simulation is then carried out using a wide range of (possibly time-dependent) boundary condition for CC, CV or constant power operation or combinations thereof connected by custom abort conditions. BEST will compute the compute the 3d solution fields for concentrations and potentials as well as derived quantities like current density, fluxes, local overpotentials or heat production. These are stored in regular intervals in vtk-format. Additionally, BEST aggregates time series of derived global quantities such as cell potential, plating risk or different contributions to the overpotentials.

Figure 4: Simulation snapshot of a charging simulation itaking into account the electrode microstructure with a blended cathode (right). Color-code denotes the local state of lithiation.

Besides the described model on the electrode microscale, BEST implements additionally a homogenized version in the sense of a pseudo-4-dimensional model (p4D), which allows to the efficient computation of a full cell (possibly including tabs and multiple layers).

- **Electrolyte Wetting**

A time-consuming production step in cell manufacturing is the wetting process that follows the filling of the liquid electrolyte into the cell housing. In this process, the electrolyte, driven by capillary forces and external pressures, must penetrate the porous structure of the electrodes and the separator as homogeneously as possible. The time required for this process, the influence of external conditions, and the homogeneity of the electrolyte distribution can be simulated using a model based on the Navier-Stokes-Brinkmann equation that includes a term for the capillary forces. With this approach the transient three-dimensional electrolyte distribution in a sheet stack of a cell can be computed. Besides an estimation of the required wetting time, the electrolyte distribution can be used in electrochemical simulations (cf. above). The model is implemented in ITWM's

Figure 5: Simulated electrolyte distribution during wetting from four edges of the cell stack.

FLUID software.

- **Simulation software technical sheet**

Name of the code	BEST & FLUID
Version of the code to be integrated	2024
Partner(s) involved	Fraunhofer ITWM
Contact person(s)	Jochen Zausch (jochen.zausch@itwm.fraunhofer.de)
Nature of the software program: solver, pre-processor, post-processor, homogenization tool...	Pre-processor, solver
OS: Windows/Linux and eventually Linux distribution: any, Debian, Suze, Fedora, Ubuntu, Linux Mint, Gentoo ...	<i>Linux</i> : RedHat 8+ and derivatives; <i>Windows</i> : 10+
Minimum memory requirement	16 GB+
Major software requirement	none
Access mode to the code: library, executable	Executable
Licence (free or commercial, GPL, LGPL)	Commercial
Open-source or not	No
The specific language(s) in which the code is written: C, C++, Fortran, Python	C++
What kind of API is proposed (one function, several functions) ; for each used function, give a short description	None
Execution with single- or multiple-calls	Single call
Execution mode : sequential, parallel, distributed	Sequential and thread-parallel (OpenMP)
Whether compilation is necessary for each run	No; (optionally user-defined functions for certain parameter dependencies can be implemented and compiled at run-time)
addendum	-
Website	http://itwm.fraunhofer.de/best

- **Model information flow : inputs and outputs**

Purpose	Geometry input
Number of files	3
Short description	Voxel mesh with ids indexing the different materials; voxel dimensions; id assignment to material class
File structuration formats*	Plain text
Storage format*	ASCII and xml
Input/Output/Code	Input

Purpose	Model and solver parameters
Number of files	3-5
Short description	Parametrization for model parameters and other solver settings
File structuration formats*	Plain text
Storage format*	Xml (optionally also cpp)
Input/Output/Code	Input

Purpose	Variable parameters
Number of files	Arbitrary
Short description	Description of concentration-dependent parameters (eg. OCV)
File structuration formats*	Plain text
Storage format*	ASCII (optionally also cpp)
Input/Output/Code	Input

Purpose	Local solution fields
Number of files	Arbitrary
Short description	Spatial fields of solution variables (concentrations, potentials) and derived quantities (eg. Current densities, overpotentials, etc). One file per output time step
File structuration formats*	Mixed plain text and binary
Storage format*	Vtk
Input/Output/Code	Output

- **Physical quantities: type and description**

Material	Input quantity	Unit	Type
Active material (anode/cathode)	Li diffusivity	cm ² /s	Scalar (possibly depending on state of lithiation)
	Electronic conductivity	S/cm	Scalar (possibly depending on state of lithiation)
	Open-circuit voltage	V	Scalar depending on state of lithiation
Electrolyte	Li diffusivity	cm ² /s	Scalar (possibly depending on salt concentration)
	Ionic conductivity	S/cm	Scalar (possibly depending on salt concentration)
	Transference number	1	Scalar (possibly depending on salt concentration)
CBD (anode/cathode)	Effective electronic conductivity	S/cm	Scalar
	Effective ionic conductivity	S/cm	Scalar (possibly depending on salt concentration)
	Effective ionic diffusivity	cm ² /s	Scalar (possibly depending on salt concentration)
	Porosity	1	Scalar
Separator	Porosity	1	Scalar
	MacMullin number/tortuosity	1	Scalar
Intercalation reaction	Exchange current density	A/cm ²	Scalar (possibly depending on salt concentration and state of lithiation)
Electrode (anode/cathode)	Geometry	m	3d voxel data describing material distribution in simulation domain; alternatively: image stack

Output	Unit	Type
Cell voltage	V	Time series
Electrode potentials	V	Time series
Overpotentials	V	Time series
SOC	1	Time series
Current	A	Time series
Concentration	mol/cm ³	Scalar field
Potentials	V	Scalar field
Intercalation flux	mol/(s cm ²)	Vector field
Ion flux	mol/(s cm ²)	Vector field
Electronic current density	A/cm ²	Vector field
Ionic current density	A/cm ²	Vector field
Heat production	W/cm ³	Scalar field
Local electrode Pot. vs Li (Plating condition)	V	Scalar field

Lattice-particle model for multiphysical simulation of electrodes

- **Context**

The lattice-particle model is designed to simulate multiphysical phenomena in a microstructured domain, namely a representative volume element (RVE) composed by particles. This model accounts for the influence of local microstructural features, including particle geometry and distribution, on the macroscopic transport properties and mechanical behavior. The primary application is to predict ion diffusion and structural integrity in heterogeneous particle-based materials, particularly useful for understanding the electrode's performance during operation conditions and can be also extended to manufacturing processes such as drying or calendering. The methodology of the lattice-particle model encompasses two primary components: microstructure generation and the lattice-particle formulation. The microstructure is generated using a "take-and-place" approach to produce a representative volume element (RVE) that captures the heterogeneous nature of the material. The process begins by defining the four key phases of the microstructure: active material (AM), additives (conductive), binder, and pores. Active material, typically graphite-based for anodes, is characterized by its volume fraction and sieve curve data. Additives, usually carbon-based, have specific volume fractions, sieve curve, and physical properties. The binder is described by its own volume fraction, while the pores are represented by porosity, which governs ion transport. The construction of the microstructure involves placing particles within a cubic domain (RVE) sequentially, starting with the largest to optimize packing density. Partial overlap between particles is accepted to reflect realistic microstructural features. Once the particles are placed, the microstructure undergoes voxelization and segmentation, enabling computational simulations. Each voxel is assigned to a material phase based on particle and binder placement. This methodology is suitable for both anode and cathode designs, ensuring compatibility across battery electrode architectures.

Figure 1. Representative volume elements (RVEs) of graphite anode with different compositions.

The lattice-particle model currently accounts for the transport and mechanical behaviour by discretizing the microstructure and incorporating particle-particle and particle-pore interactions. The microstructure is discretized into lattice points corresponding to material phases. Particle interactions, including binding and diffusivity adjustments, are defined based on established models, such as those by Yu et al. (1999), Wang et al. (2010), and Chouchane (2019).

- **Methodology**

The solving scheme addresses governing equations for ion diffusion and diffusive-mechanical problems, which are solved iteratively following a finite element method (FEM) discretization and an explicit integration scheme. Transport properties, such as diffusivity, are assigned to lattice points based on their material phase, and linear systems are solved to obtain ion concentration and flux distributions following Fickian diffusion:

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} = 0$$

where c is the concentration of the diffusing species, t is time, and \mathbf{J} is the ion flux that is defined as:

$$\mathbf{J} = -D \left(\nabla c - \frac{\Omega \cdot c}{R \cdot T} \nabla \sigma_h \right)$$

where \mathbf{D} is the diffusion matrix in the active material, R is the gas constant, Ω is the ion partial molar volume, T is the absolute temperature, σ_h is the hydrostatic stress and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor.

The characterization of the electrodes involves extracting diffusivity and tortuosity factors to describe the effective transport properties of the microstructure. This methodology ensures accurate representation of the electrode's mesoscale features, enabling predictions of ion transport dynamics under various operation conditions.

The diffusive-mechanical problem is solved by means of a continuum damage formulation, which reads as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = (1 - d) \mathbf{D}_0^{\text{el}} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{el}}$$

where \mathbf{D}_0^{el} is the initial (undamaged) elasticity matrix. In the formulation, the elastic stiffness degradation is characterized by the degradation parameter, d . The degradation parameter can take values ranging from zero (undamaged material) to one (corresponding to total loss of strength).

We assume an isotropic expansion in the definition of the diffusion-induced strain tensor, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^d$:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^d = \frac{\Omega}{3} (c - c_0) \mathbf{I}$$

Figure 2. Effective diffusion for different RVE compositions.

● **Model technical sheet**

Name of the code	Pekken3D
Version of the code to be integrated	2024
Partner(s) involved	Loyola
Contact person(s)	Francisco Montero-Chacón (fpmontero@uloyola.es)
Nature of the software program: solver, pre-processor, post-processor, homogenization tool...	Pre-processor, solver, post-processor
OS: Windows/Linux and eventually Linux distribution: any, Debian, Suze, Fedora, Ubuntu, Linux Mint, Gentoo ...	Any
Minimum memory requirement	4 GB
Major software requirement	Matlab R2020a or later. All libraries included.
Access mode to the code: library, executable	library
Licence (free or commercial, GPL, LGPL)	FNL
Open-source or not	No
The specific language(s) in which the code is written :C, C++, Fortran, Python	Matlab
What kind of API is proposed (one function, several functions) ; for each used function, give a short description	None
Execution with single- or multiple-calls	Single call.
Execution mode : sequential, parallel, distributed	Sequential and parallel (OpenMPI)
Whether compilation is necessary for each run	No
addendum	-
Website	-

● **Model information flow**

Purpose	Geometry input
Number of files	1
Short description	Number of phases; volume fractions of the phases; particle sieve curve (size and percentage); electrode thickness; electrode geometry
File structuration formats*	Plain text
Storage format*	*.m
Input/Output/Code	Input

Purpose	Local material properties
Number of files	1
Short description	For every material phase defined in the Geometry Input, define: diffusivity; volumetric expansion coefficient; elastic modulus; Poisson's ratio
File structuration formats*	Plain text
Storage format*	*.m
Input/Output/Code	Input

Purpose	Model and solver parameters
Number of files	1
Short description	Parametrization for model parameters and other solver settings
File structuration formats*	Plain text
Storage format*	*.m
Input/Output/Code	Input

Purpose	Local solution fields
Number of files	User-defined

Short description	Plots and tables of vector and scalar fields of solution variables: ion concentration; displacement; stress. Time-step is user-defined.
File structuration formats*	CSV
Storage format*	CSV; PNG
Input/Output/Code	Output

● **Physical quantities: type and description**

Inputs	Type	File
Volume fractions (-)	Array N×1 (N: number of phases)	Geometry.m
Porosity (-)	Scalar	Geometry.m
Sieve curves (μm,-)	Matrix 3×M (M: number of discretizations)	Geometry.m
Electrode thickness (μm)	Scalar	Geometry.m
Local diffusivities (cm ² /s)	Array N×1 (N: number of phases)	LocalProps.m
Local volumetric expansion coefficients (1/var)	Array N×1 (N: number of phases)	LocalProps.m
Local elastic moduli (GPa)	Array N×1 (N: number of phases)	LocalProps.m
Local Poisson's ratio (-)	Array N×1 (N: number of phases)	LocalProps.m

Outputs	Type	File
RVE structure (positions of the particles, μm)	Array M×3 (M: number of particles)	Output.m
Global diffusivity (cm ² /s) in each direction	Array 3×1	OutputDiff.m
Global Elastic Modulus (GPa) in each direction	Array 3×1	OutputMech.m
Damage (-)	Array M×N (M: number of elements, N: time-step)	OutputMech.m
Displacement field (μm)	Array M×N (M: number of particles, N: time-step)	OutputMech.m

Molecular modelling and simulation of redox-flow electrolyte properties

- **Context**

The work will be conducted within T2.5 (Integrated multiphysics modelling of redox flow batteries). Due to staffing at NMBU, it will be carried out from M18 to M27 (June 2025 – March 2026). The involved team members will be Maria Bashir (NMBU) and David Fertig (NMBU), with Martin Horsch (NMBU), Kristin Tøndel (NMBU), Mathijs Janssen (NMBU) and possibly Eirik Valseth (SIMULA) and Kristian Berland (NMBU) in an advisory capacity.

- **Modelling objective**

The aim is to quantify the dependence of key thermodynamic and transport properties of the homogeneous vanadium redox flow battery (VRFB) electrolytes as a function of boundary conditions, composition (preparation) and state of charge.

The macroscopic degrees of freedom (input quantities) to be considered are:

- Temperature and pressure within the range of VRFB operating conditions.
- Total amount of sulfate (mainly represented by hydrogen sulfate).
- Total amount of vanadium ions.
- State of charge (represented by the ratio between vanadium ions at the two oxidation states present in the respective electrolyte).

The obtained simulation output quantities are:

- Thermodynamic properties including density, heat capacity, isothermal compressibility, and speed of sound.
- Linear transport properties, including shear viscosity, diffusion coefficients, thermal and electric conductivity.

The above will be determined both for the anolyte and the catholyte of the VRFB.

The nonlinear transport regime, interfacial properties, the influence of the electric field on thermodynamic and transport properties, and deviations from bulk behaviour in surface-near regions remain out of scope for this line of work.

Surrogate models created on this basis (T3.5, M19-M33) will be used to generate input parameters for (the simulations and the surrogate models created from) dissipative particle dynamics using DL_MESO, conducted by UKRI within T2.4 and T2.5 and aggregated within

T3.5, and continuum multiphysics models using FEniCSx, conducted by SIMULA and NMBU within T2.4 and T2.5 and aggregated within T3.5.

- **Methodology**

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations will be conducted in the isothermal-isobaric (NpT) ensemble using the ms2 code (<http://www.ms-2.de/>) and molecular models which are rigid, i.e., neglecting internal degrees of freedom. Molecular models from the literature will be used. It is possible that reparameterizations will be conducted if strictly needed; however, resources within the project are limited, therefore, such work will be kept at a minimum.

Water models are known to be of limited accuracy. Therefore, two water models, SPC/E and TIP4P-FB, will be used in all cases, and simulation results will be compared. To mitigate the error due to water model deviations from real water properties, common correction schemes will be employed, including normalizing densities with respect to the density of pure water (independently both for the model and for the real fluid) and an additive correction for the heat capacity to account for partially excited internal degrees of freedom.

- **Model technical sheet**

Name of the code	ms2
Version of the code to be integrated	Development version from repository
Partner(s) involved	NMBU and possibly SIMULA
Contact person(s)	Martin Thomas Horsch (martin.thomas.horsch@nmbu.no)
Nature of the software program: solver, pre-processor, post-processor, homogenization tool...	MD and MC solver, including tools for preprocessing and postprocessing
OS: Windows/Linux and eventually Linux distribution: any, Debian, Suze, Fedora, Ubuntu, Linux Mint, Gentoo ...	Any POSIX-compliant system; might also work on other systems, but this is unusual.
Minimum memory requirement	4 GB
Major software requirement	Compiler and MPI environment matching the HPC environment. Usually these are already in place on the HPC system.
Access mode to the code: library, executable	Code compiled on and for the target system.
Licence (free or commercial, GPL, LGPL)	Free for academic use; on a case-by-case negotiation basis for non-academic use. Co-owned by project partner RPTU. The present use case is considered to fulfill the conditions under which ms2 is free for use.
Open-source or not	No
The specific language(s) in which the code is written :C, C++, Fortran, Python	Fortran
What kind of API is proposed (one function, several functions) ; for each used function, give a short description	None
Execution with single- or multiple-calls	Single call
Execution mode : sequential, parallel, distributed	Parallel execution, either MPI-parallel or employing hybrid parallelization
Whether compilation is necessary for each run	No, not for each run, but once for each target architecture
addendum	-

Website	https://www.ms-2.de
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- **Model information flow: Inputs and outputs**

We refer to the documentation at <https://www.ms-2.de/software/input-output.html>.

- **Physical quantities: type and description**

We refer to the *Modelling objective* section above.

- **Methodology**

The models and software described herein are for the proposed modeling of redox flow batteries at Simula Research Laboratory. At the heart of Simula's contribution to the simulation campaign lies the FEniCSx software. FEniCSx is an open-source software tool for simulating the partial differential equations (PDEs) arising in any application desired. The software provides a framework for solving the PDEs using finite element methods (FEM), which are particularly suitable for capturing the complex, multi-physics interactions in electrochemical systems as well as its potentially challenging geometries. In the context of redox flow batteries, the governing equations of interest include mass transport, electrochemical kinetics, fluid dynamics, and electric potential. However, as the project advances, the PDEs of interest may be updated.

Mass transport within redox flow batteries is described by the Nernst-Planck equations, which account for ion diffusion, migration, and convection within the electrolyte. Electrochemical reactions occurring at the electrode surfaces are modeled using the Butler-Volmer equations to represent the kinetics of redox reactions. Fluid flow through porous electrodes and channels can be represented by the Navier-Stokes equations or its surrogates for porous media flow, while the electric potential distributions within the system are governed by Poisson type equations.

The simulation process in FEniCSx involves defining the geometry of the battery components, such as electrodes, electrolyte channels, and flow regions, and creating a finite element mesh for these domains. The PDEs and their couplings are then mathematically expressed, along with appropriate boundary and initial conditions. Numerical solvers utilizing appropriate FEM schemes are used to resolve these equations, accounting for nonlinearities and coupling effects. For time-dependent simulations, implicit or explicit time-stepping schemes may be employed. Once the system has been solved, post-processing and visualization tools allow for the analysis of variables like species concentrations, potential distributions, and fluid flow patterns.

When applied to redox flow batteries, this approach enables the simulation of ion transport under specified electric potential gradients and flow fields. Potential distributions can be computed by solving the Poisson equation, while fluid flow dynamics are incorporated through the Navier-Stokes equations. Electrochemical reaction kinetics can also be integrated into the model through boundary conditions derived from the Butler-Volmer equations.

FEniCSx operates with a well-defined structure for inputs and outputs, which streamlines the process of solving PDEs and analyzing results. The primary inputs in FEniCSx include the problem domain geometry, which is discretized into a mesh, and the mathematical description of the governing equations expressed in the Unified Form Language (UFL). Users also specify material properties, such as diffusivity or conductivity, as well as boundary and initial conditions that define the system's constraints and starting states. Additionally, time-stepping parameters are required for transient simulations, including the total simulation time and the size of time

steps. Other than the mesh, which FEniCSx can accept in virtually any format, the other inputs are generally described in Python scripts.

The outputs of a FEniCSx simulation typically include numerical solutions to the PDEs over the defined domain, such as fields for species concentration, electric potential, or velocity. These solutions are provided at the nodes or elements of the mesh, enabling detailed spatial analysis. FEniCSx also supports exporting results to common data formats such as XDMF or VTK, which can be visualized using external tools like ParaView. For time-dependent simulations, outputs include time-series data that track the evolution of the solution, allowing users to investigate dynamic behaviors. Users can further customize outputs by extracting derived quantities of interest, such as fluxes, gradients, or integrated values over specific regions.

- **Model technical sheet**

Name of the code	FEniCSx
Version of the code to be integrated	0.9 or later
Partner(s) involved	SIMULA and NMBU (maybe others)
Contact person(s)	Eirik Valseth (eirikva@simula.no)
Nature of the software program: solver, pre-processor, post-processor, homogenization tool...	Solver (though generalizable as FEniCSx is based on Python scirpts)
OS: Windows/Linux and eventually Linux distribution: any, Debian, Suze, Fedora, Ubuntu, Linux Mint, Gentoo ...	<i>Linux, Windows, and Apple OS</i>
Minimum memory requirement	NA
Major software requirement	Python compiler
Access mode to the code: library, executable	library
Licence (free or commercial, GPL, LGPL)	Free - LGPL
Open-source or not	Yes
The specific language(s) in which the code is written :C, C++, Fortran, Python	Python, C, and C++
What kind of API is proposed (one function, several functions) ; for each used function, give a short description	NA
Execution with single- or multiple-calls	Single call.
Execution mode : sequential, parallel, distributed	Sequential,parallel, or distributed (MPI and openMP, and CUDA)
Whether compilation is necessary for each run	No
addendum	-
Website	https://fenicsproject.org

- **Model information flow : inputs and outputs**
 - **File structure**

File name	Input
Extension	txt
Short description	Spatial characterization of the electrode particles.
File structuration formats*	Four columns of float numbers separated by single space.
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Input

File name	Mesh.XX (for example)
Extension	Multiple (user defined)
Short description	Mesh file
File structuration formats*	Depends on format, most available accepted or easily converted to be
Storage format*	Multiple
Input/Output/Code	Input

File name	Output.XX (for example)
Extension	Multiple (user defined)
Short description	Output files from simulations
File structuration formats*	Depends on format, most available accepted or easily converted to be
Storage format*	Multiple
Input/Output/Code	output

- **Physical quantities : type and description**

FEniCSx as a general software framework will use whichever quantities that are relevant for the model at hand.

DFT modelling of carbon felt electrode materials for vanadium redox flow batteries

- **Context**

DTU and NMBU will collaborate to supply the required density functional theory (DFT) simulations with T2.4 and T2.5. DTU will distribute its work evenly between T2.4 and T2.5, with the bulk of it being carried out between M13 and M24 (January – December 2025); José María Castillo Robles will be involved as a team member, and Ivano Castelli in an advisory capacity. NMBU will mainly contribute to T2.5, from M21 to M27 (September 2025 – March 2026), as a consequence of an analysis of the staffing situation at NMBU; Øven Andreas Grimenes will be involved as a team member, Kristian Berland in an advisory role.

- **Modelling objective**

Two objectives have been agreed:

- Develop a better understanding, suitable for quantitative modelling at a higher level, of the influence of functionalizations of the carbon felt material (carbonyl, epoxy, hydroxyl, carboxyl groups, among others) on vanadium reactivity at the surface.
- Model potential degradation pathways by which the above mentioned substituents are eliminated from the surface, both in dry mode during shelf life (before use in the battery) as well as in operation in contact with the highly acidic electrolyte fluid.

- **Methodology**

One of the key research interests in batteries involves investigating the solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI). Understanding SEI formation at the atomistic scale provides valuable insights for effective battery design. The dynamics of the electrode-electrolyte interactions play a crucial role in the SEI formation mechanism. To explore these dynamics, we employ ab-initio molecular dynamics (AIMD) and DFT calculations to analyse the electrode-electrolyte interface and the presence of chemical reactions.

AIMD simulations allow us to reveal reaction mechanisms, the formation of intermediate species, and the molecular dynamics at the interface. DFT complements these insights by providing equilibrium geometries of molecules at the interface, their electronic structures, reaction energies, and transition states. These results allow us better to understand the thermodynamics and kinetics of SEI formation processes. Kinetic Monte Carlo simulations can further extend the timescales of the simulations, allowing us to study longer-term processes beyond the timescales accessible by AIMD.

Furthermore, structural properties of SEI components obtained through DFT, such as lattice parameters, bond lengths, and relative stability, offer insights into the crystalline or amorphous nature of the SEI. AIMD also facilitates the calculation of diffusion coefficients, providing insights into the ion mobility within the SEI layer.

The application of external electric fields or voltages can also affect the processes present during the SEI formation, leading to charge transfer between the electrode and electrolyte, and altering the reaction mechanisms and stability of SEI components. The applied voltage potential can also modify the free energy landscape of the system, impacting the thermodynamics and kinetics of chemical reactions at the interface.

Including these voltage effects in the simulations allows for the study of phenomena such as electrolyte decomposition, changes in ionic or electronic conductivity, and the SEI growth dynamics under a voltage, capturing the SEI evolution over time during cycling.

Finally, by combining these theoretical insights with experimental data, a more complete picture of the SEI can be developed, linking atomic-scale processes to macroscopic battery performance. These atomistic Insights not only enhance our understanding of battery behaviour but also provide guidance for optimizing materials and operating conditions to improve efficiency and durability.

Relevant publications:

- 1) B. H. Sjølin, W. S. Hansen, A. A. Morin-Martinez, M. H. Petersen, L. H. Rieger, T. Vegge, J. M. Garcia-Lastra, and I. E. Castelli, PerQueue: Managing Complex and Dynamic Workflows, *Digital Discoveries* **3**, 1832 (2024).
- 2) X. Qin, A. Bhowmik, T. Vegge, and I. E. Castelli, Computational Investigation of LiF Formation at Graphite–Electrolyte Interfaces, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **16**, 29347 (2024).
- 3) B. H. Sjølin, P. B. Jørgensen, A. Fedrigucci, T. Vegge, A. Bhowmik, and I. E. Castelli, Accelerated Autonomous Workflow for Antiperovskite-based Solid State Electrolytes, *Batteries & Supercaps* **2023**, e202300041 (2023).
- 4) I. E. Castelli, M. Zorko, T. M. Østergaard, P. Martins, P. P. Lopes, B. K. Antonopoulos, F. Maglia, N. Markovic, D. Strmcnik, and J. Rossmeisl, The Role of an Interface in Stabilizing Reaction Intermediates for Hydrogen Evolution in Aprotic Electrolytes, *Chem. Sci.* **11**, 3914 (2020).
- 5) F. T. Bølle, N. R. Mathiesen, A. J. Nielsen, T. Vegge, J. M. Garcia Lastra, and I. E. Castelli, Autonomous Discovery of Materials for Intercalation Electrodes, *Batteries & Supercaps* **3**, 488 (2020).
- 6) D. Strmcnik, I. E. Castelli, J. G. Connell, D. Haering, M. Zorko, P. Martins, P. P. Lopes, B. Genorio, T. Østergaard, H. Gasteiger, F. Maglia, B. K. Antonopoulos, V. R. Stamenkovic, J. Rossmeisl, and N. M. Markovic, Electrocatalytic Transformation of HF Impurity to H₂ and LiF in Lithium Ion Batteries, *Nature Catalysis* **1**, 255 (2018).

- **Description of the model**

This model investigates the surface reactions and adsorption of vanadium species on graphene felt electrodes, which are crucial for optimizing the performance of vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFB). The graphene felt is represented as a periodic slab structure, capturing key features such as defects, edge sites, and potential functional groups. Vanadium species are modelled explicitly, and their interactions with the surface are evaluated under varying conditions of surface coverage. The computational study aims to provide insights into the adsorption energies, reaction pathways, and energy barriers for vanadium-related processes. This supports the design of more efficient electrodes by linking microscopic surface properties to macroscopic experimental observations.

The DFT simulations are conducted using VASP (Vienna ab-initio simulation package) and leverages density functional theory (DFT). Key methodologies include:

- 1 **Kohn-Sham DFT** to compute the ground-state electron density and total energy.
- 2 **Dispersion-corrected functionals** (e.g., vdW-inclusive methods such as DFT-D3 or vdW-DF) to model non-covalent interactions critical for accurately describing adsorption on graphene.
- 3 **Nudged Elastic Band (NEB) method** for determining reaction energy barriers along transition pathways.
- 4 **Thermodynamic analysis** of adsorption and reaction energetics, including the effects of temperature and surface coverage.

The workflow involves:

- **Model Preparation:** Construct periodic graphene slabs, including defects and relevant functional groups, and optimize the structures.
- **Adsorption Studies:** Analyze binding energies and configurations for vanadium species on different sites.
- **Reaction Mechanism Exploration:** Identify and compute energy barriers for key reactions using NEB.
- **Output Analysis:** Evaluate charge density differences and identify active surface regions.

- **Model technical sheet**

Name of the code	VASP
Version of the code to be integrated	5 or later
Partner(s) involved	DTU and NMBU
Contact person(s)	ivca@dtu.dk
Nature of the software program: solver, pre-processor, post-processor, homogenization tool...	Solver
OS: Windows/Linux and eventually Linux distribution: any, Debian, Suze, Fedora, Ubuntu, Linux Mint, Gentoo ...	<i>Linux</i>
Minimum memory requirement	NA
Major software requirement	Fortran, C compiler (e.g. gcc)
Access mode to the code: library, executable	library
Licence (free or commercial, GPL, LGPL)	Commericla
Open-source or not	No
The specific language(s) in which the code is written :C, C++, Fortran, Python	NA
What kind of API is proposed (one function, several functions) ; for each used function, give a short description	NA
Execution with single- or multiple-calls	Single call.
Execution mode : sequential, parallel, distributed	Sequential,parallel (MPI))
Whether compilation is necessary for each run	No
addendum	-
Website	https://www.vasp.at/

- **Physical quantities: type and description**

Inputs	Type	Source
Graphene slab structure	CIF file	Generated or DB
Vanadium species geometries	XYZ file	Generated
Pseudopotentials (PAW datasets)	Files	VASP database
NEB calculation parameters	Text file	Input script

Outputs	Type	File Name
Adsorption energies and configurations	Scalars, POSCARs	AdsorptionResults.txt
Reaction energy barriers	Scalars	ReactionBarriers.txt
Charge density differences	CHGCAR files	ChargeDiff.plots

Redox flow battery pore-scale (mesoscopic) simulations

- **Methodology**

The models and software described herein are for the proposed modelling of redox flow batteries at UKRI STFC, specifically the transport of ions in liquid electrolytes towards the surface of pores in carbon felt. UKRI STFC will predominately use DL_POLY_5 [1], an open source particle dynamics code capable of modelling electrolytes and carbon surfaces at the mesoscale using Dissipative Particle Dynamics (DPD) [2]. This software is sufficiently general-purpose to enable various scenarios to be modelled, including (1) the study of transport properties for the electrolytes (anolyte and catholyte), (2) identification of the minimum distance required from a carbon surface (measured from ion concentration profiles), and (3) the effects of surface functionalization including embedded charges and defects due to heat treatment of the felt. It should be noted that while we cannot directly consider the redox reaction itself in these simulations, the effect of the carbon surface on local ion concentrations relative to bulk electrolytes may give some indication of reaction rates.

DPD is a mesoscopic variant of molecular dynamics (MD) that hinges upon determining forces acting on particles based on interaction potentials and applying those forces over small time durations (timesteps). These potentials are predominately pairwise in nature and are chosen to represent how the particles would interact based on their contents, often considered as ‘coarse grains’ (collections of atoms or molecules). DPD adds to these with additional pairwise forces for dissipation and randomized Brownian motion, providing temperature control in the form of a momentum-conserving thermostat that does not disrupt any applied flow to the particles.

The electrolytes will be predominately represented as water beads interacting with an ‘ n DPD’ potential [3], a modified form of the interactions most commonly used in DPD calculations [2] to enable more realistic thermodynamic behaviour. Each water bead will consist of 5 molecules of water and predominately interact with an n DPD potential parameterised to give the correct liquid density, self-diffusivity and viscosity at the battery’s operating temperature [4]. The ionic species in the electrolytes – vanadium and sulphate (part of sulphuric acid) – will be treated as ion-water complexes and will interact similarly to water but with additional charges that interact electrostatically. Protons (hydrogen ions) will be modelled individually and interact with water and sulphate beads with a potential to represent proton transfer effects [5].

The carbon felt will be represented as a layer of beads interacting hydrophobically with other species [6] but frozen in place so it does not move. The typical diameter of a pore (tens of micrometres) compared with the size of bead (under a nanometre) means that flat surfaces for the felt will suffice. As the flow speed of electrolyte through the pore is much smaller than thermal particle motion for the operating temperature, ion diffusion will dominate over flow effects and the minimum required distance from the carbon surface will be the concentration boundary layer. For simulations examining the effects of surface functionalization, an additional region of frozen beads with bulk electrolyte will be included at the opposite end to the carbon surface.

The presence of the carbon pore will also lead to variations in local permittivity for the electrolytes. This can be accounted for by adding dipoles to the water beads [7], which can be selected to provide the correct relative permittivity for pure water. Preliminary simulations indicate that this approach should provide realistic dipole moment distributions for the required coarse-graining level. To speed up calculations with polarizable water, we intend to apply the dipoles by using rigid bodies (a solver for which is supplied in DL_POLY_5) rather than attaching charges to water beads using flexible bonds.

The process of carrying out simulations using DL_POLY_5 involve the creation of configurations defining the initial positions of particles, defining the interactions between particles ('beads' in the context of mesoscale modelling), and setting simulation controls. These involve creating input files in text-based formats that DL_POLY_5 reads in at the start of a calculation. The main input file driving the simulations is named CONTROL, which specifies system properties such as temperature, numbers and size of timesteps, implementation of electrostatic interactions etc. The FIELD file specifies the contents of the simulation box and the interactions between beads: while the former will vary between different simulations, the interactions should not drastically change and can be reused. The CONFIG file provides the initial positions of particles for each simulation.

CONFIG files for simulations of bulk electrolytes will be created by selecting the box size and adding beads at random positions: no numerical issues would result if any beads are placed on top of one another due to 'soft' interactions. The configurations for simulations with carbon felt require positioning of carbon beads to either represent a flat surface or to include defects and/or embedded charges. Simulations of the concentration boundary layer can take configurations of bulk electrolytes from the trajectories of previous calculations and add these as frozen beads. All of these and their associated FIELD files will be created using Python scripts (yet to be written).

The DL_POLY_5 simulations will generate HISTORY files consisting of configuration snapshots at user-specified time intervals as a trajectory. These can be visualised graphically using molecular plotting packages such as VMD, used as (partial) configurations for subsequent simulations or post-processed using Python scripts to obtain e.g. concentration profiles.

- **References**

- 1) IT Todorov, W Smith, K Trachenko and MT Dove, DL_POLY_3: new dimensions in molecular dynamics simulations via massive parallelism, *Journal of Materials Chemistry* **16** (20), 1911 – 1918 (2006), DOI: 10.1039/b517931a
- 2) RB Groot and PB Warren, Dissipative particle dynamics: Bridging the gap between atomistic and mesoscopic simulation, *Journal of Chemical Physics* **107** (11), 4423 – 4435 (1997), DOI: 10.1063/1.474784
- 3) VP Sokhan, MA Seaton and IT Todorov, Phase behaviour of coarse-grained fluids, *Soft Matter* **19** (30), 5824–5834 (2023), DOI: 10.1039/D3SM00835E
- 4) M Seaton, V Sokhan and I Todorov, *Development of enhanced interactions for highly coarse-grained materials*, IN: Proceedings for ASME 2024 7th International Conference

on Micro/Nanoscale Heat and Mass Transfer, V001T08A010 (2024), DOI: 10.1115/MNHMT2024-132397

- 5) M-T Lee, A Vishnyakov and AV Neimark, Modeling proton dissociation and transfer using dissipative particle dynamics simulation, *Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation* **11** (9), 4395 – 4403 (2015), DOI: 10.1031/acs.jctc.5b00467
- 6) A Vishnyakov, R Mao, M-T Lee and AV Neimark, Coarse-grained model of nanoscale segregation, water diffusion, and proton transport in Nafion membranes, *Journal of Chemical Physics* **148**, 024108 (2018), DOI: 10.1063/1.4997401
- 7) S Chiacchiera, PB Warren, AJ Masters and MA Seaton, Coarse-grained polarizable soft solvent models, with applications in dissipative particle dynamics, *Journal of Chemical Physics* **161**, 174115 (2024), DOI: 10.1063/5.0226871

- **Model technical sheet**

Name of the code	DL_POLY_5
Version of the code to be integrated	5.2.0
Partner(s) involved	UKRI
Contact person(s)	Michael SEATON (michael.seaton@stfc.ac.uk)
Nature of the software program: solver, pre-processor, post-processor, homogenization tool...	Solver
OS: Windows/Linux and eventually Linux distribution: any, Debian, Suze, Fedora, Ubuntu, Linux Mint, Gentoo ...	Any (Linux preferred)
Minimum memory requirement	~160 bytes per particle (1.26MB for smallest calculation, ~5 GB for largest calculation)
Major software requirement	Fortran compiler, MPI (optional)
Access mode to the code: library, executable	Source code
Licence (free or commercial, GPL, LGPL)	LGPL-3
Open-source or not	Yes
The specific language(s) in which the code is written :C, C++, Fortran, Python	Fortran
What kind of API is proposed (one function, several functions) ; for each used function, give a short description	None
Execution with single- or multiple-calls	Single call.
Execution mode : sequential, parallel, distributed	Sequential and parallel (MPI)
Whether compilation is necessary for each run	No
addendum	-
Website	https://gitlab.com/ccp5/dl-poly

- **Model information flow : inputs and outputs**
 - **File structure**

File name	CONTROL
Extension	None
Short description	Simulation controls
File structuration formats*	Keywords (words separated by underscores) with values and units as specified in DL_POLY_5 documentation ³
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Input

Name of file	FIELD
Extension	None
Short description	Simulation contents (numbers of particles) and interaction details (functional forms and parameters)
File structuration formats*	Blocks starting with keywords and followed by lines with further keywords and values as specified in DL_POLY_5 documentation ⁴
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Input

File name	CONFIG
Extension	None
Short description	Simulation configuration: initial positions of particles
File structuration formats*	Entries (lines) consisting of particle type, number and Cartesian coordinates, as specified in DL_POLY_5 documentation ⁵
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Input

³ https://ccp5.gitlab.io/dl-poly/UserManual/data_files/input_files.html#the-control-file

⁴ https://ccp5.gitlab.io/dl-poly/UserManual/data_files/input_files.html#the-field-file

⁵ https://ccp5.gitlab.io/dl-poly/UserManual/data_files/input_files.html#the-config-file

File name	HISTORY
Extension	None
Short description	Simulation trajectory: configuration snapshots taken during calculation at specified time intervals
File structuration formats*	Similar to CONFIG file, outlined in DL_POLY_5 documentation ⁶
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Output

File name	ConfigGenerator (name to be determined)
Extension	.py
Short description	Python script to generate CONFIG and FIELD files for simulations
File structuration formats*	Plain text
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Code

File name	ConcentrationProfile (name to be determined)
Extension	.py
Short description	Python script to convert simulation trajectories in HISTORY files to ion concentration profiles
File structuration formats*	Plain text
Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	code

File name	Concentration (to be confirmed)
Extension	.dat (to be confirmed)
Short description	Ion concentration profile determined using post-processing Python script from simulation trajectory in HISTORY file
File structuration formats*	Tabulated columns of values

⁶ https://ccp5.gitlab.io/dl-poly/UserManual/data_files/output_files.html#the-history-file

Storage format*	ASCII
Input/Output/Code	Output (post-processed)

- **Physical quantities : type and description**

Inputs	Type	File
Interactions: types and parameters [$\text{kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ etc., depends on interaction types]	Scalars	FIELD
Simulation box size/volume [\AA^3]	Array 3 by 3 (unit cell vectors)	CONFIG
Charges on particles [e]	Scalars	FIELD
Relative permittivity	Scalar	CONTROL

Outputs	Type	File
Simulation trajectory: series of simulation snapshots (positions: \AA)	Array $3 \times N$ (N: number of particles)	HISTORY
Concentration profile [mol/L]	Array $m \times N$ (m: number of ion types, N: number of distances from carbon surface)	Concentration.dat

3. Conclusions

This deliverable represents the foundational effort in structuring the simulation activities within WP2, providing an initial plan for the models to be developed and used in the project. While the current simulation campaign plan provides a comprehensive inventory of the models and tools identified by the partners, it also highlights the iterative and evolving nature of this work. As mentioned, further refinement and integration will be necessary to bring the state of modelling readiness, now complete at the single-model level, to the hierarchically upper level of integrated workflow description.

The current process maps and the technical model descriptions are essential starting points for the next phase: building detailed simulation workflows. These workflows will integrate the identified models, account for interdependencies, and ensure compatibility between tools to facilitate horizontal interoperability. The outputs of this work will contribute to the digital twin development.

This further work of iterative refinement of the process maps and workflows will be informed by advancements in understanding the feasibility of simulating specific process steps and the alignment of the tools with the evolving requirements of the use cases. The planned deliverable D2.3 will show the finalization of this efforts, providing finalized workflows that will seamlessly interface with the broader objectives of WP5. As such, this deliverable is not only a milestone but also a dynamic reference point ensuring the continuity and cohesion of WP2's contributions to the BatCAT project.